

Termitophilous rove beetle dataset bibliography

in “Termite nest evolution fosters social parasitism by termitophilous rove beetles”

Nobuaki Mizumoto^{1,2*}, Thomas Bourguignon^{1,3}, Taisuke Kanao⁴

1: Okinawa Institute of Science & Technology Graduate University, Onna-son, Okinawa, 904-0495, Japan

2: School of Life Sciences, Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ, 85287, USA

3: Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences, Kamycka 129, 16521, Praha, Czech Republic

4: Faculty of Science, Yamagata University, Yamagata, Japan

*. Correspondence: Nobuaki Mizumoto; nobuaki.mzmt@gmail.com

Data S1:

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